

INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF ALL POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the effects of processing conditions on the interfacial properties of all-polypropylene (all-PP) composites. Using a recently optimised process, a lower melting temperature (T_m) grade of PP can be coextruded onto the surface of high modulus PP tapes during production. By controlling the tape drawing conditions and subsequent composite processing parameters, it is possible to tailor the interface of these composites. Experimental analysis has been completed revealing the interfacial properties of different microcomposite models.

KEYWORDS: Interface (interphase), adhesion, T-peel, damage, lap shear, self-reinforced composites.

INTRODUCTION

Ease of recycling favours mono-component systems rather than complex blends and alloys. Polypropylene(PP), is the major polymeric construction material of the future in view of its impressive growth figures of the past years. PP can also be easily processed, modified and recycled using existing technology, and so adapted to many applications. However, due to its low mechanical properties, PP has to be reinforced with glass or natural fibres to meet the high demands on stiffness and strength in engineering applications. The presence of these 'foreign' reinforcements within PP composites creates problems for traditional thermo-mechanical recycling of PP. Burning glass fibre reinforced PP leaves a residue in furnaces, while grinding results in rapid erosion of grinding equipment. Natural fibre reinforced PP are easier to burn but generates new problems due to swelling and degradation of fibres in use. At the same time they show no mechanical advantage. The aim of this research is to develop all-polypropylene (all-PP) composites, viz. PP reinforced with oriented PP tapes rather than glass fibres. Such an all-PP composite has specific ecological advantages since upon recycling, a PP blend is obtained which can be reused to make all-PP composites, or alternatively, can be cascade recycled for other PP-based applications. In recent years, the ethos of eco-design has become a more integral part in the development of new products and the redevelopment of existing ones. This is partially due to greater environmental awareness within industry, but is also guided by government legislation enforcing reuse and recycling. The issue of recycling is of particular relevance to the automotive industry with the recent End-of-Life Vehicle Directive aiming to increase the rate of recycling to at least 85% by average weight by 2006 [1].

The production of highly oriented, high strength polymer fibres by the careful control of processing routes has been well documented over the past 30 years [2-5]. Polypropylene in particular has been oriented into uniaxial and biaxial films [6, 7], as well as fibres, via a range of drawing routes [8-10]. PP can be melt spun and drawn to give oriented fibres, with tensile moduli of ~ 18 GPa and tensile strengths of ~ 720 MPa achievable [11, 12]. As the polymer fibre is deformed there is a transition from a random molecular structure to a highly oriented structure, with polymer molecules becoming aligned in the direction of deformation [5]. This structural transition results in an increase in stiffness due to the inherent stiffness of polymer molecules along their axis. As draw ratio increases, there is a reduction in molecules acting transversely, holding the oriented regions together and so as orientation increases there

Table 1. Typical Mechanical Properties of Engineering Fibres

	Density g.cm ⁻³	Strength MPa	E Modulus GPa	Specific Strength MPa/g.cm ⁻³	Specific Modulus GPa/g.cm ⁻³
E-glass	2.6	2000	70	770	27
Flax	1.4	600	40	430	28
PP fibres	0.9	650	18	720	20
PP tapes in this research	0.7	450	15	640	21

is a simultaneous decrease in transverse strength of the fibre. Typical mechanical properties for polypropylene fibres are shown in Table 1, compared to E-glass and flax fibres, which are typical reinforcements for PP. It is clear that the strength and stiffness of polypropylene cannot directly compete with that of E-glass, but due to the low density of polypropylene the specific properties are comparable with E-glass and superior to flax.

Standard manufacturing routes cannot be directly applied to construct a monocomponent thermoplastic composite. The main difficulty is the combination of reinforcement and matrix, without melting the oriented phase and thus losing stiffness and strength developed in drawing. One possible solution is fibre impregnation with molten thermoplastic matrix. The temperature of the molten matrix has to be relatively low to prevent heat transfer and total melting of the fibre. Thus the temperature of the polymer melt can only be slightly above the melting temperature and so has a very high viscosity, which makes it very difficult to wet out the fibres. Hence this production route of melt impregnation of multifilament yarns would not be very cost effective and result in higher costs and processing times.

The microstructure of high modulus thermoplastic fibres is highly oriented and if the fibre is heated relaxation of the molecules would occur with molecules re-establishing their preferential isotropic structure. It is possible to prevent this relaxation by constraining the fibre, hence preventing this reorganisation and by doing this the fibre can be prevented from melting. To determine the shear strength of model composites, micro debond tests were performed by measuring the debond strength of pulling PP fibres out of a PP matrix droplet [12], as shown in Fig. 1. A graph of these results, debonding force against embedded length, is shown in Fig. 2. These tests have revealed that these composites have a shear strength of 9 MPa, compared to the 9.3 MPa theoretical value for bulk polypropylene. Failure of these fibres will always fail a cohesive mode in the oriented fibre phase rather than in the bulk matrix. This proves an excellent adhesion between fibre and matrix for these single fibre composites.

Figure 1. PP droplet on a PP fibre for micro-debond test

Figure 2. Graph of fibre pull-out force vs embedded area

The ‘hot compaction’ process developed at the University of Leeds [13] is a possible route to the production of monocomponent composites and has also been investigated for a range of polymers as well as polypropylene [14-16]. The hot compaction process works by stacking layers of polymer fibres, and the subsequent application of heat and pressure. A small amount of the exterior of the fibre melts, and on the application of pressure fills the interfibrillar voids. This process is complicated by a very small processing window, ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) [17], which makes it a difficult process to apply industrially. In order to increase this temperature processing window, a new approach has been applied in this research. This new approach uses coextruded polypropylene *tapes* combined with constrained heating to create all-PP composites. The coextruded PP tapes consist of a PP core with a thin ‘skin’ of a different grade of PP. The skin layer has a significantly lower melting temperature than the PP used in the core. This coextruded tape is drawn in a two stage drawing process which provides orientation and resulting stiffness and strength within the core of the tape. The tape can then be filament wound to make unidirectional materials or woven into a fabric before heat and pressure are applied to consolidate the tapes into a composite. This thin coextruded layer can be considered analogous to coating a glass with its matrix material, whose sole purpose is to facilitate excellent bonding between the fibres; the mechanical properties of the tape are due to the highly oriented core. The coextruded ‘matrix’ layer has a melting temperature below that of bulk PP, and so when combining constraining with coextrusion technology, a temperature processing window of $>30^\circ\text{C}$ can be obtained, compared to the 2°C window previously reported for standard hot compaction [17]. The melting point of the ‘skin’ layer can be tailored by changing the grade of PP used or by altering the drawing parameters. The thickness of the skin can be controlled and is typically in the region of 5% thickness on either side of the tape. This skin can also be used to carry any functional additives such as pigments and stabilisers. The large processing window also means that composites can be created with complex thickness variations; a reduced sensitivity to temperature gradients is important in PP sheets which are inherently poor thermal conductors. Tape dimensions can be controlled, but typical tapes have a thickness of $\sim 60\ \mu\text{m}$ and a width of $\sim 2\ \text{mm}$. The tapes described in this paper have a draw ratio, $\lambda=14$, and possess a strength and stiffness of $\sim 450\ \text{MPa}$ and $15\ \text{GPa}$ respectively (see Table 1). As an interesting consequence of drawing these tapes, there is a considerable decrease in density due to the creation of microvoids within the tape [3]. This effect will be discussed further in a forthcoming paper [18].

INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES

Unidirectional composite specimens have been produced via a filament winding route. Coextruded tapes are wound onto a steel mandrel which is then subjected to heat and transverse pressure in a hot press. The self-constraining action of winding prevents shrinkage within the tape and the application of transverse pressure by the hot press ensures good consolidation. Following the consolidation process, tensile tests were performed on strips of this composite laminate with tape orientation of 0° and 90° to the testing direction. Tests were performed in accordance with ASTM3039, using an Instron tensile testing machine

Figure 3. Graph of unidirectional properties vs consolidation temperature

1. Fig. 3 shows the effect of consolidation temperature on the modulus, E , of unidirectional specimens at 0° . (x_I) and 90° to the testing direction. It is apparent that there is a significant increase in modulus, E , at 0° and 90° to the testing direction. This is also apparent in the tensile strength, σ , of the specimens. The increase in tensile strength, σ , is also apparent in the tensile strength, σ , of the specimens. The increase in tensile strength, σ , is also apparent in the tensile strength, σ , of the specimens.

Figure 4. Schematic of T-peel test

T-PEEL MICROCOMPOSITES

To isolate the performance of the interface, T-Peel tests were performed on all-PP ‘micro-composites’. T-peel specimens are created by consolidating two pieces of tape and then peeling them apart at a 180° angle (see Fig. 4). This test simulates mode I failure and provides useful information on the strength and the location of failure. There are three distinct regions of failure for these peel tests, shown in Fig. 5(i), (ii), and (iii). At relatively low bonding temperatures, as the skin layer becomes tacky, there is little bonding (Fig. 5(i)). As consolidation temperature is increased, the two adjacent skins bond and peel away from the oriented core (Fig. 5(ii)). At consolidation temperatures above the T_m of the skin, the two adjacent skin layers bond and failure occurs within the highly oriented core (Fig. 5(iii)). This transition from adhesive to cohesive failure occurs when the melting temperature of the skin is reached. As is seen in Fig. 5(iii), cohesive failure results in a very large surface area and the crack bridging of large numbers of microfibrils. Fig. 7 shows a graph of peel force compared to increasing consolidation temperature for two different tapes. In this graph a maximum peel strength is reached equal to the cohesive peel resistance of the oriented core

(i) (ii) (iii)
Figure 5. SEM images of T-Peel surfaces:(i) adhesive failure, (ii) transition and (iii) cohesive failure

Figure 6. Effect of consolidation temperature on T-peel force

structure for each tape. As in the transverse failure of unidirectional composites, the failure is due to the oriented core structure rather than the interface. With increasing draw ratio, there is an increase in orientation of molecules, and so there is a lower cohesive strength within the oriented layer. Also noticeable is a decrease in the onset of adhesion with increasing draw temperature. This is because at lower drawing temperatures, the skin layer also becomes oriented in the drawing process and so the constraining effect is exerted on the skin layer during consolidation. When the draw temperature is sufficiently high to allow for remelting of the skin during drawing, the skin remains unoriented and so is not effectively constrained during consolidation. This allows melting of the skin at lower consolidation temperatures.

SINGLE LAP SHEAR MICROCOMPOSITES

Single lap shear specimens were also performed using single tape ‘microcomposites’. Mode II failure is often the dominant failure mode for fibre composites and so is particularly relevant to this research. In

single lap shear test

Figure 8. Effect of bond length on single lap shear strength

traditional composite systems, shear stress transfer is most effective near the ends of the fibre and this leads to a fibre length of maximum efficiency for stress transfer within the composite [19, 20]. This ‘critical fibre length’ provides information about the strength of interfaces subjected to mode II failure. By bonding specific lengths of two adjacent tapes, the effect of bonded length can be established for these coextruded tapes (see Fig. 7). Fig. 8 shows a graph of applied force against bonded layer length. From this graph, it is clear that there is non-linear relationship between bond strength and bonded area, supporting the critical fibre length theory for all-PP composites. In this case, the shear strength corresponds to ~10.5 MPa which is slightly higher than that seen for monoextruded PP. This may be due to the increased shear strength of the skin layer. As in T-peel tests, there is a transition from adhesive failure within the unoriented skin layer to cohesive failure within the oriented core layer, with increasing consolidation temperature.

FALLING WEIGHT IMPACT PROPERTIES

This effect of temperature on composite failure modes has wide implications to applications of all-PP composites. In order to apply this knowledge to actual composite systems, impact properties have been investigated for plates made from stacked, woven fabric layers, compacted at a range of temperatures. It is clear that impact testing a composite will result in a combination of failure modes. Penetrative impact energy absorbed is shown in Fig. 9. As compaction temperature increases, energy absorbed during impact decreases, reaching a plateau phase; above this temperature, impact strength decreases as molecular relaxation occurs. This proves that impact energy has an inverse relationship with interfacial strength. Tapes compacted at lower temperatures have a weaker interface and impact damage occurs via a tape pull-out mechanism. As tape interface strength increases, failure occurs through a tape breaking mode. The tape pull-out mechanism seen at lower compaction temperatures results in larger areas of damage within the composite and so leads to greater energy absorption than more highly consolidated specimens. Again there is a transition from interfacial to cohesive failure with increasing consolidation temperature. With increasing draw ratio, there is also a decrease in impact performance, probably due to decreased tape cohesion. There is no loss of tape strength with increasing compaction temperature (Fig. 3) and so this cohesive failure may dominate again.

Figure 9. Effect of consolidation temperature on penetrative impact properties

CONCLUSION

All-PP composites possess unique interfacial properties which are ultimately defined by the choice of consolidation parameters. This allows the user to tailor the interfacial properties depending on the desired application. Consolidation of coextruded all-PP tapes is a fast and low cost process, in which the matrix is extruded as a 'coating' on the surface of the reinforcement. The tapes are subsequently welded together to form all-PP composites with excellent levels of adhesion between the 'skin' PP matrix and oriented PP core. Ultimately, in each of these tests, the interfacial strength exceeds the strength within highly oriented structure, and it is transverse failure within the highly oriented PP core which limits the transverse strength of all-PP composites. Because the coextruded 'skin' can be very thin, the resultant composites can have very high fibre volume fraction (>90%) compared to glass-fibre-reinforced PP (20-50%). All-PP composites can already compete or even out-perform glass reinforced PP for structural and impact applications, and the combined low cost and low density of all-PP composites make them a very attractive, recyclable alternative to glass reinforced PP.

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